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The Impact of Scientific Research on Sustainable development: case of Arab Region

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Abstract

This paper examines the following issues (1) scientific research at international level, and in the Arab region as a mechanism for sustainable development; (2) the essence of scientific research and its outputs in Arab higher education institutions, and the weak relationship between it and the services companies; (3) the impediments of research in the Arab region, and the possible methods of overcoming the problem. The findings of this research paper includes: (1) lack of adequate research funding from within the Arab region; (2) there is weak relationship between research institutions, the industrial and the private sectors. The nonprofit sector is still very weak in the Arab region; and (3) brain drain syndrome of the Arab region tends to negatively affect research productivity, as well as development.

Introduction

Scientific research and economic development are center to the way people in different societies consume resources, use land, and water at different rates according to their level of wealth or poverty. The level of sustainability in the Arab region also depends on the amount of technologies available to citizens, their society's culture norms, social, economic and other political factors (Dibie 2008; Withgott and Brennan 2008). One other dilemma in the Arab region, however is that sustainability has not been viewed to require the maintenance of fully functioning ecological systems, because people in the area cannot sustain civilization without sustaining the natural system that nourish the region.

Currently, a growing societal problem in the context of unsustainable development meets with conflicts of interest. The actual implementation of sustainability research, innovations and technologies, has only been mildly successful in the Arab region. Sustainable development demands nothing less than a radical change in the modes of consumption, production, technology, and decision-making. Research and technological development is essential for designing the innovation and solutions needed to make real progress on the challenges of sustainable development. Scientific research for civil purposes is considered as the main pillar towards attaining a sustainable development in any modernized society. The number of published scientific papers and registered patents during the past decades is considered as one of the indicators of the development in the Arab region. The results of scientific research have important impacts on creativity and on the industrial, agricultural and technological development in the region. Unfortunately, there have been very

little differences in industrial, agricultural and technological growth over the past decades in the Arab region. This of course has not increased the national income, styles of human living, and the level of welfare for people in the region. Modern and developed societies usually do not hesitate in supporting research activities in order to ensure its continued scientific and economic development and to keep a high standard of living.

It is worth mentioning here that scientific research always needs funds to cover the required human and technical resources alongside the availability of a creative mind that finds creative solutions for existing problems. In an analytical view of the scientific research reality in the Arab world, we find that the scientific research expenses compared to the total national income is equivalent to 0.2% while the contribution of the private organizations is absent. Compared with developed countries, 2.5% of their Gross Domestic Product (GDP) goes for research and development (R&D) activities, to which the private sector contributes 80% of the overall expenditure. This is considered one of the problems that stand in the way of scientific research in the Arab world. This lack of funding problem and increases the gap between the Arab and western industrialized nations. It has also galvanized the Arab scholars and scientists to leave their Arab countries for the western industrial nations. Consequently, there is a need to establish new channels in which the private sector should be involved along with the governmental sector to support and fund scientific research projects in the Arab countries.

Sustainable development in the Arab Region must be considered within the broad economic, political, institutional, environmental, cultural and ethical context. In order to harness science, technology and innovation for sustainable development, it is important to understand the dynamic interplay of the issues and challenges in sustainable development. The Arab region is characterized by a singular and largely uniform arid/semi-arid ecological zone from the Atlantic Ocean to the Persian Gulf. The region is also rather homogeneous in language and culture. The main engine of economic growth is oil. The challenges to sustainability are also similar, given the rates of illiteracy and relatively lower investments, human resources and capacity in science and technology. There is therefore, great promise for a high degree of regional co-operation and for evolving a shared vision for sustainability and concerted actions.

Some of the high priority issues for sustainable development in the Arab region are: (1) gender equity; (2) education and capacity building in science and technology; (3) environmental issues - fresh water, desertification, dry land biodiversity and coastal zones; (4) Alternative and renewable sources of energy; (5) Cross-cutting themes of governance and S&T policy (Withgott and Brenan, 2008).

Since the Rio Summit in 1992, major accomplishments have been made in the Arab region towards the achievement of sustainable development, particularly in the areas of education, health and improved standards of living. However, a number of obstacles continue to face the Arab countries in the long-term implementation of sustainable development. Examples are the absence of peace and security, the continuation of foreign occupation in some Arab lands, poverty, illiteracy, population growth, and the debt burden. Other factors include the arid nature of the region, the scarcity of water resources and limited agricultural land, the moderate capabilities of the academic and research centers, in addition to the relatively recent experience of civil society.

Based on the Ministerial Declaration on Sustainable Development issued in Cairo on 25 October 2001, the League of Arab States adopted a comprehensive regional approach, through the Council of Arab Ministers responsible for the environment and other specialized ministerial councils and in cooperation with international, regional and Arab organizations. This approach aims at developing a regional program for sustainable development. The League of Arab States tends to be ready to collaborate with the international community to assist the Arab countries to face the challenges and the obstacles that exist in the region.

The Agenda 21 initiative is aimed at addressing the challenges faced by the Arab countries to achieve sustainable development. It asserts the commitment of the Arab countries to implement Agenda 21 and the development objectives included in the Millennium Declaration and the outcome of the World Summit on sustainable development, taking into consideration the principle of common but differentiated responsibility. The initiative seeks to enhance the participation of the Arab countries with the aim of strengthening their efforts in realizing sustainable development, particularly in the light of globalization and its impacts, as well as finding a mechanism for financing the programs for environmental protection and sustainable development.

The initiative is considered as a framework for the implementation of programs and activities using the available resources in the Arab countries. The initiative will also be implemented through building partnerships with the other regions, groups and international organizations and institutions. Further, this is part of the international framework for achieving sustainable development. This initiative is intended to involve all the stakeholders at the national and regional level, particularly civil society organizations and the media and NGOs.

This paper examines the level of research that has been conducted in the Arab region of the Middle East. It explores the following issues (1) scientific research at international level, and in the Arab region as a mechanism for sustainable development; (2) the essence of scientific research and its outputs in Arab higher education institutions, and the weak relationship between it and the services companies; (3) the impediments of research in the Arab region, and the possible methods of overcoming the problem. The findings of this research paper includes: (1) lack of adequate research funding from within the Arab region; (2) there is weak relationship between research institutions, the industrial and the private sectors. The nonprofit sector is still very weak in the Arab region; and (3) brain drain syndrome of the Arab region tends to negatively affect research productivity, as well as development.

Conceptual Framework

Sustainable development extends beyond environmental protection and natural resource conservation. It includes, governmental actions affecting human health and safety, transportation, agriculture, food production, education, energy use, population growth, national and international growth, chemical, and geophysical system and the protection of vital global ecological systems (Kraft, 1996; Rosenbaum, 2008).

According to Water Rosebaum (2008) and Withgott and Brennan (2009) the humanity challenges is to develop solutions that further our quality of life while protecting and restoring the environment that support the human beings all

over the world. These scholars contend that the way we tackle the sustainable development challenge will largely determine the nature of our lives in the twenty-first century and beyond. The recent advocates of sustainable development arose from the recognition that society's poorer people often suffer the most from environmental degradation. This realization is beginning to open more government, business, industries and nongovernmental organization efforts in several Arab countries.

Several Arab nations have struggling with the challenges of improving of improving their society's response to sustainable development, particularly in the form of environmental policy. The policy response however, requires careful appraisal of the problems and a serious effort to determine what kind of solutions hold the greatest promise. Governments in these Arab nations have a diversified set of tools in their policy repertoires. According to Robert Dibia (2008) these government tools include regulation, creation of public trusts, taxation, education, subsidies, purchase of goods and services, rationing, research, charging fees, and investment.

There are several assumptions about the sustainable development concept. In this paper sustainability is defined as leaving our children and grandchildren a world as rich and full as the world we live in now. That is, conserving Earth's resources so that our descendants will enjoy them as well as we have. This means developing solutions that work and benefit everyone in the society in the long run. This requires maintaining fully functioning ecological system, because we cannot sustain human civilization without sustaining the natural systems that nourish it (Withgott and Brennan 2009; Dibia 2008).

Research conducted during the past 30 years by international agricultural research organizations has been successful in boosting productivity and providing enough food to feed the world. However, problems of food scarcity, poverty, and natural resource degradation have persisted in the Arab region (Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research, 2000). As a result, a new management and research approach called integrated natural resource management (INRM) is emerging. This is an evolving research and development (R&D) approach that combines the interconnected goals of poverty reduction, food security, and environmental sustainability. It is defined as " ... the conscious process of incorporating multiple aspects of natural resource use into a system of sustainable management to meet explicit production goals of farmers and other uses (e.g., profitability, risk reduction) as well as goals of the wider community sustainability" (Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research, 2000). International R&D has also entered a new phase in which these multifaceted efforts must be accomplished with the efficient use of financial resources. During the last decade, slower growth in international research funding has resulted in calls to demonstrate research impact. For example, the real growth rate of funding to the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) declined from 4.0% per year in the 1980s to 0.5% per year since 1990 (Alston et al. 2000). To meet the triple challenge of (1) demonstrating more diverse impact with (2) fewer financial resources and (3) showing how this can be achieved, INRM requires a more holistic impact assessment approach that evaluates not only economic changes but also changes in the environment, people, and their organizations.

A European report on science and technology indicates that access to scientific and technological knowledge produced through research and the

ability to exploit it are becoming increasingly strategic and decisive for the economic performance of countries and regions in the competitive globalized economy. The 50 leading science and technology (S &T) countries have enjoyed long-term economic growth much higher than the other 130 countries of the rest of the world (Rosebaum 2008). Between 1986 and 1994 the average growth rate of this heterogeneous group of countries was around three times greater than that of the rest of the world. The average economic wealth per capita of these 50 countries has grown by 1.1% per year. On the other hand, the per capita income of the group of 130 countries – which perform less well in education, science and technology- has fallen over the same period by 1.5% per year. These trends provide a new division of the global economy that is based on access to knowledge. Technology education as a matter of fact, would challenge us on how to better achieve sustainable development” in the world (European Second Report on S &T Indicators 1997).

Research Methodology

An investigation on Arab universities and extra-university research institutes was conducted through published literature, peer-reviewed journals, reports, conference proceedings and monographs. The aim was to obtain a general view of the quantity, quality, and dissemination of sustainability research within the public sector. A region wide survey was administered to identified relevant institutions and scientists engaged in sustainability research. An unstructured interview was conducted to some heads of public scientific institutes. It inquired about the involvement of the respective institution in sustainability research and/or education, and about relevant players within this institution.

The second step was the review of literature and the analysis of data that was collected from internet about the quantity and quality of the researchers' involvement in sustainability research and education. The analysis involves finding out their perceived obstacles and potentials, and financial resources devoted to research all over different regions in the world. In some cases we use two groups of analyses in the region, Gulf Countries and Mediterranean region. The Mediterranean region includes eight Arab countries or territories: Algeria, Egypt, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Palestine, Syria and Tunisia, while the Gulf includes six Arab countries: Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates (UAE).

One limitation of the comparison in our analysis is that we use data and information from different sources and different years; the scarcity of data and information covering all countries limited our attempt to use a unified source. For instance there was no data covering some of Arab countries like Libya, Palestine and Sudan.

Human and Financial Input Indicators

In terms of both financial and human S&T input/resource indicators (research) there were some differences between the Arab Gulf and Mediterranean countries and other countries around the world. Table I shows that on the whole both financial and human S&T input indicators in these regions lag behind those of the advanced and leading developing countries.

Average government expenditure per student is just US\$2,500, compared to US\$14,200 in Spain. However, student enrolment in the Arab region is estimated to be 25 percent of the population, much higher than many other developing countries. The enrolment of women is also high in some countries, including Saudi Arabia and the Gulf states. Table 1 shows the science and technology resource indicators of the Arab countries capered to those of the rest of the world.

Table 1. Science and Technology Resource indicators of the Arab and World countries

Country	Public expenditure on education as % of GDP ^a		Public expenditure on education as % of government expenditure ^a		R&D expenditure as % of GDP ^a	Number of scientists and engineers in R&D (per milli. population) ^a	Number of patents ^{a,b}	High technology exports as % of manufactured exports ^a	
	1990	1998-2000	1990	1998-2000	1996-2000	1996-2000	1990-1999	1990	2001
<i>Gulf Countries</i>									
Bahrain	4.2	3.0	14.6	11.4	Na	Na	2	0	0
Kuwait	4.8	Na	3.4	Na	0.2	212	27	4	1
Oman	3.1	3.9	11.1	Na	Na	8	3	11	3
Qatar	3.5	3.6	Na	Na	Na	591	0	0	0
Saudi Arabia	6.5	9.5	17.8	Na	Na	Na	103	0	Na
UAE	1.9	1.9	14.6	Na	Na	Na	15	0	Na
Average Gulf	4.0	4.4	12.3	11.4	0.2	270	25	2.5	1
<i>Mediterranean countries₁</i>									
Algeria	3.5	Na	21.1	Na	Na	Na	Na	0	4
Egypt	3.7	Na	Na	Na	0.2	493	38	0	1
Lebanon	Na	3.1	Na	11.1	Na	Na	Na	Na	3
Morocco	5.3	5.5	26.1	26.1	Na	Na	Na	0	11
Syria	4.1	4.1	17.3	11.1	0.2	29	3	0	1
Tunisia	6.0	6.8	13.5	17.4	0.5	336	Na	2	3
Average Mediterranean	4.9	4.9	19.5	16.4	0.3	286	20.5	0.4	3.8
Norway	7.1	6.8	14.6	16.2	1.7	4,112	97	8	12
Sweden	7.4	7.8	13.8	13.4	3.8	4,511	285	13	18
UK	4.9	4.5	Na	11.4	1.8	2,666	76	23	31
Rep. Of Sou. Korea	3.5	3.8	22.4	17.4	2.7	2,319	931	18	29
Singapore	Na	3.7	Na	23.6	1.1	4,140	12	39	60
China	2.3	2.1	12.8	Na	0.1	545	793	0	20

Sources: a UNDP (2003) b United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) website: <http://www.uspto.gov>. Patent data for Korea, Norway, Singapore, Sweden and the UK obtained from UNDP (2003) and refers to patents granted in 1999 to residents per million people. For China and all Arab countries, patent data was obtained from USPTO during 1991-1999 and refers to the number of registered US patents where the inventor of the patent is resident in the selected countries.

In Qatar, for example, 46.2 percent of eligible women enroll in tertiary education, but only 13.7 percent of eligible men. Currently, some 200 universities employ 140,000 faculty to teach 3.6 million students. Despite these encouraging figures, the region's growing population means that enrollment is expected to rise to 5.6 million by 2015, which will require an extra 110,000 faculty.

Table 2: Expenditure on Research in the Arab Countries and the World 2002-2004

Country	Expenditure on Research (in Billion)	Expenditure as % of GDP	Year
Sweden	10	4.27	2002
Fenland	5	3.5	2002
Japan	107	3	2002
United State of America	275	2.5	2002
Israel	6.1	4.7	2002
Arab Countries	1.7	0.3	2004
Latin America & Caribbean	21.3	0.6	2004
South East of Asia	48.2	2.7	2004

Table 3: Expenditure on Education per year

Individual's share in Expenditure on Education		Expenditure per student	
Arab Region	Israel	Arab Region	Developed c
\$ 240	2500	2500	45000

Table 4: Universities Expenditure on Research (Million Dollars)

American Universities		Arab Universities	
University	Expenditure	University	Expenditure
Miami (2004-2005)	269	Jordan Science and Technology	0.5
Colombia (1996)	232	King Abdul-Aziz University (2002)	4
Nevada (1996)	80	Sultan Qaboos University	1.3
Central Florida – Optic College	20	King Suad University (2000)	2

Financial Indicators

In particular, tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 shows that the financial resources devoted to S&T, as measured by the percentage share of GDP spent on R&D, are poor in the Arab countries compared to both advanced and leading developing countries like Singapore and Korea. For instance, in the period 1996–2000, the Arab Mediterranean and Gulf countries devoted an average of only 0.3% of their GDP to R&D whereas Sweden, one of the leading advanced industrial countries,

spent 3.8% of GDP on R&D. However, spending on education, as measured by percentage of both GDP and total government expenditure was found to be similar for the Arab countries and the advanced countries. Comparing S&T indicators between the two Arab regions shows that the Mediterranean countries on average perform better than the Gulf countries in terms of expenditure on both education and R&D as percentage of GDP.

Investigation of the distribution of R&D in Gulf and Mediterranean Arab countries indicates that the public sector is responsible for the majority of R&D activities, accounting for 49.4% and 80.4% of all R&D institutions respectively (figure 1). Next to public sector, universities contributed 43.5% and 13.4% of R&D institutions in Gulf and Mediterranean countries respectively; the private sector makes only a minor contribution, accounting for 7.0% and 6.2% of R&D institutions respectively. The Mediterranean countries appear to be more dependent on the public sector than the Gulf countries. This reflects a lack of incentives for private sector institutions to invest in R&D in the Mediterranean compared to the Gulf. This compares poorly to most of the industrialized countries, where more than half of R&D expenditure is financed by industry (OECD 1997).

Human Resources Indicators

Table 1 show that there are a low number of scientists and engineers in R&D in the Gulf and Mediterranean countries compared to both advanced and leading developing countries. Moreover, the OECD (1997) Second European Report on S&T Indicators shows that there are proportionally 10 times fewer R&D personnel in the Mediterranean countries than in the European Union. When comparing the two Arab regions, it is the Mediterranean countries that show a marginally better performance than the Gulf countries in terms of the number of scientists and engineers in R&D.

In terms of the human resources devoted to R&D, defined by the number of full-time equivalent (FTE) researchers, and their distribution within R&D organizations (figure 1), we find that the majority of FTE researchers are employed by public and university sectors. The percentage share of FTE researchers in the public sector is estimated to be 49.2% and 74.9% in the Gulf and Mediterranean Arab countries respectively. Next to the public sector, it is the university sector that has the largest percentage share of FTE researchers: at 49.3% and 23.6% respectively; the private sector accounts for only 1.4% and 2.6% of total FTE researchers in the regions. As with the distribution of R&D institutions, it is the Mediterranean countries that appear to be more dependent on the public sector for FTE researchers than the Gulf countries. Again, it is the lack of incentives for private sector institutions to hire FTE researchers that leads to this disparity.

In addition, there are fewer human resources in S&T in both the Gulf and Mediterranean Arab countries compared to more developed countries, shown in figures 2 and 3. The Arab countries score poorly compared to Korea and Singapore for the Harbison Myers Index, technical enrolment index, engineering enrolment index, gross enrolment ratio at tertiary education and the share of tertiary students in science, mathematics and engineering. The only exception (not shown in figure 3) is the share of tertiary students in science, mathematics and engineering in Algeria, which is higher compared to both advanced and

developing countries (UNDP 2004). When comparing average skill indicators for the Arab Gulf countries with those of the Mediterranean, figures 2 and 3 indicate that, on average, the Mediterranean countries perform better. Additional information from Lall (1999) and UNDP (2004) indicate that all these skill indices are especially high in Lebanon and Kuwait, while the gross enrolment ratio at tertiary education is highest in Egypt and Lebanon followed by Qatar and Bahrain. The share of tertiary students in science, mathematics and engineering is highest in Algeria, followed by Syria, Oman, Morocco, the UAE and Tunisia. With the aforementioned exception of Algeria, enrolment in science, mathematics and engineering is lower than enrolment for all other subjects in both Mediterranean and Gulf countries. In addition, school-leaving age is highest in Tunisia, Qatar, Bahrain and Lebanon.

Patent Applications

Table 1 shows the low number of patent applications made by countries in both of the Arab regions compared to advanced and leading developing countries like Singapore, Korea and China. In light of our earlier findings, this can be attributed to the Arab countries' low percentage share of GDP spent on R&D and the small number of scientists and engineers in R&D. The low number of patent applications implies a low level of innovative activities across both Arab Mediterranean and Gulf countries compared to both advanced and developing countries.

Scientific Publications

Table 5 indicates that, in the Arab Mediterranean countries, Egypt has the best percentage share of total world scientific publications. However, the average share of all Arab Mediterranean countries remains very low compared to those of the United States, European top 15 and non-Arab Mediterranean countries. Moreover, the percentage share of both total papers published and number of citations in publications in the region is much lower for any of the Arab Mediterranean countries than the non-Arab Mediterranean countries (Turkey and Israel specifically). Again, Egypt leads the Arab Mediterranean countries in this indicator, followed by the group of Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia and then the group of Albania, Cyprus, Lebanon, Malta and Syria. Furthermore, in the period 1985–1995, it is Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia that display the most coordination; cooperation and networking with the European top 15 countries in terms of internationally co-authored papers.

Despite, the increasing importance of international cooperation, there is very limited cooperation among scientists in both Arab Gulf and Mediterranean countries as indicated by the number of joint publications and co-authorships (table 4). In particular, it is scientists from the Gulf countries who lag behind, accounting for less than 2% of worldwide cooperation. Zahlan (1999a) finds that in 1990, co-authorship within the Gulf countries was only 1.4% of all co-authored papers; this increased to 3% in 1995. Such limited regional cooperation is also true for the Mediterranean countries, for instance in 1995 scientists in the Maghreb countries of Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia published 1,206 publications. Of these, 769 were co-authored with scientists from other countries

yet only 11 included scientists from two Maghreb countries. Furthermore, only one out of the 11 did not involve an OECD partner.

Table 5: Technology output indicators by share of the world's scientific publication output, published papers, citations and internationally co-authored Papers

Countries	Share in world's publication output in all scientific fields combined (%)		Share of published paper and citation in the Mediterranean countries (%)				Mediterranean countries' share of internationally co-authored papers with EUR 15 (%)			
	1985-1989	1990-1995	1985-1989	1990-1995	1985-1989	1990-1995	1985-1989	1990-1995	1985-1989	1990-1995
	Paper s	Citatio n	Paper s	Citatio n	Paper s	Citatio n	Paper s	Citatio n	Paper s	Citatio n
Egypt	0.27	0.29	16.5	16.5	5.7	15.6	8.0	7.5	9.7	11.2
Algeria/ Morocco/ Tunisia	0.08	0.13	4.6	4.6	2.4	6.7	40.4	56.4	54.7	58.7
Lebanon/ Syria/ Malta/ Albania/ Cyprus	0.03	0.04	1.9	1.9	0.7	2.0	23.7	30.7	21.1	48.5
Average Arab Mediterranean	0.13	0.15	7.7	7.7	2.9	8.1	24.0	31.5	28.5	39.5
Average Non-Arab Mediterranean	0.65	0.72	38.6	38.6	45.6	37.9	9.3	12.4	9.4	12.3
EUR 15	30.42	33.92	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na
USA	36.33	35.82	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na	Na

Source: Adapted from RASCI Data: Science Citation Index, OECD (1997). Pp. 455-460.

Table 6: Scientific Cooperation: Total Number of Publications and Joint Publication in the Gulf and Maghreb countries.

Country	Total number of published papers		Number of joint papers		Co-authored with GCC partners		Co-authored with Arab partners		Main Arab partners	
	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995
<i>Gulf Countries</i>	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995
Bahrain	59	106	17	29	3	2	2	1	-	1
Kuwait	487	290	132	117	0	14	12	12	10	11
Oman	48	84	25	37	0	0	1	0	1	-
Qatar	48	59	19	36	2	2	6	24	6	23
Saudi Arabia	1,031	1,240	242	294	6	9	59	71	48	57
UAE	49	137	33	55	2	10	13	19	10	14
Total Gulf	1,722	2,716	468	568	13	35	93	127	75	106
	Total number of published papers		Number of joint papers		Co-authored with OECD partners		Co-authored with Arab partners		Main Partners France	
	1990	1995	1990	1995	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990
Maghrib countries	1990	1995	1990	1995	1995	1990	1995	1990	1995	1990
Algeria	172	328	137	227	120	187	4	3	90	
Morocco	240	536	153	395	132	314	0	2	90	
Tunisia	268	342	77	147	69	122	0	3	55	
<i>Total Maghreb</i>	680	1206	367	769	321	623	4	8	23.5	
Libya	58	58	31	35	11	16	3	7	11	
Total Mediterranean	738	1264	398	804	332	639	7	15	246	

Source: Adapted from Zahlan (1999a). Notes: 1 GCC – Gulf Cooperation Council including Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates. 2 The main partners for Libya are India (1990) and UK (1995).

As shown in table 4 there is an absence of scientific cooperation and co-authorship among scientists from the Gulf and Mediterranean countries as well as between them and other Arab countries. Where Gulf countries do cooperate with Arab scientists, it tends to be limited to only a small number of countries. According to Zahlan (1999a) this is because universities in Gulf countries employ professors mainly from other Arab countries. Similarly, in the Mediterranean Arab region, cooperation between Maghreb countries and other Arab scientists accounts only for 3.0% and 3.5% of all co-authored published papers in 1990 and 1995 respectively (Zahlan, 1999a). Arab countries in the Gulf have only limited cooperation with foreign institutes. For instance, while the number of the published papers in the Gulf countries increased from 1,722 in 1990 to 2,716 in 1995, fewer than a quarter were co-authored with foreign institutes.

This contrasts with the Mediterranean Arab countries, particularly the Maghreb countries that have significant cooperation with the OECD: papers co-authored with OECD countries accounted for 90.0% and 81.3% of total joint publications in 1990 and 1995 respectively. Of all the OECD countries France has the highest share of joint papers with Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia, comprising 67.0% and 61.7% of total joint papers in 1990 and 1995 respectively. These data are backed up by Zahlan (1999a) who finds that scientific workers in the Maghreb are deeply integrated with the international scientific community. So, despite the social proximity between the populations in terms of religion, language, culture and traditions, there is only limited scientific cooperation within and between the Gulf and Mediterranean Arab countries, or between them and other Arab countries. In contrast, there is active international scientific cooperation between some of the Mediterranean countries and other world countries, but this is very limited for all the Gulf countries. One reason for this is that scientific workers in the Maghreb, on an individual level, have become deeply integrated into the international scientific community but not, however, with their own national or regional economies or societies (Zahlan 1999a). More recent literature indicates the role of geographical location and proximity in relation to S&T indicators and the transfer of knowledge (Arundel and Geuna 2001). France is geographically close and also has colonial ties to Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia. Hence, we argue that it is geographic proximity rather than social proximity that drives the Maghreb countries' scientific cooperation with the international community and Europe.

Conclusion

This paper has examined the status of research in the Arab Gulf and Mediterranean countries. It contends that finding effective ways of living peacefully, healthfully, and sustainably in the Arab region will require a solid scientific research. It argues that it is paramount for the Arab people to invest in research, science and technology as well as have an understanding of the nature and social systems interdependence. The paper provided evidence of great disparity between these regions in terms of science and technology input and output indicators.

Furthermore, it argued that environmental science and research will help us to understand the Arab countries intricate relationship with their environment

and inform the people of the region ways to solve and prevent impediments that negatively affect the achievement of sustainable development in the region. Countries in both Arab regions lag behind the world's developed and leading developing countries in terms of the same input and output indicators of S&T (research). The combination of poor S&T inputs/resources together with an inadequate economic system as a whole results in the Gulf and Mediterranean countries producing poor S&T outputs/performances. Moreover, we find that most R&D and S&T activities in both Gulf and Mediterranean countries occur within the public and university sectors, while the private sector and industry make only a minor contribution. When comparing S&T input and output indicators of the Gulf countries with those of the Mediterranean, our findings indicate that in terms of most S&T input indicators (both financial and human resources) the best performances come from Mediterranean countries. That also holds for the average share of high-technology exports, GDP per capita growth, number of scientific publications and level of international cooperation, while the performance of the Gulf countries is only better with respect to number of patent filings.

Moreover, we observe that the Mediterranean countries appear to be benefiting from their geographical location and proximity to Europe, as shown by the higher levels of cooperation with the OECD and in particular France. This implies that social proximity (sharing similar religion, culture, language, values and traditions) and intra-regional linkages and networks do not matter for scientific cooperation. Instead, for some of the Mediterranean Arab countries (notably Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia), geographical proximity and external regional linkages and networks with Europe are the motivations for scientific cooperation.

Hence, our analysis indicates that in order to improve S&T performance, the Arab, Gulf, and Mediterranean countries need to invest heavily in both financial and human resources as well as to learn from the lessons of the advanced and developing S&T nations. Such investment can be more effective if they are made according to targeted, well-defined plans that connect with policies covering industry, science and technology and accompanied by an overhaul in the economic system.

None of the Gulf or Mediterranean Arab countries alone possess all the human and financial resources necessary to promote S&T. However, these countries could have a wider range of capabilities to promote S&T if they pooled and integrated their resources. Restructuring the economic systems, encouraging the private sector and implementing effective S&T cooperation and integration between all the Arab countries will most likely enhance S&T development and hence long-term harmonious development in the region.

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